

THE METHODS OF PRESENTATION ENGLISH GRAMMAR CONSTRUCTIONS ON THE BASES OF VERBAL RULE INSTRUCTIONS AND VERBAL RULE INSTRUCTIONS IN COMBINATION SCHEME RULES

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Annotation: The main aim of teaching foreign languages in all institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan and at the faculties whose major is not a foreign language is teaching so that they can get information which they need by reading texts in English concerning their profession and can communicate orally in English according to their specialty. The article is dedicated to the teaching English receptive grammar while reading math authentic literature students of mathematical faculties of universities and institutes. It is proposed teaching English grammar by verbal rule-instructions in combination schemes. There were given theoretical reasons of using schemes in teaching English receptive grammar phenomenon and were defined such principles as generalization, visualization, concretization, dynamicity, representability, simplicity.

Key words: presentation, passive construction; verbal rule-instructions in combination schemes, grammatical skills; principles; mathematical text; exercise; rule-instruction, generalization, visualization, concretization, dynamicity, representability, simplicity, consciousness, flexibility, symbol, scheme, component, auxiliary verb, quantum.

Аннотация: Основная цель обучение иностранных языков в неязыковых факультетах высших учебных заведениях Узбекистана является чтения текстов по специальности на английском языке и извлекать необходимой информации, а также вести устной беседу по своей будущей специальности. Статья посвящена обучения студентов-узбеков математических факультетов грамматическим явлениям английского языка при чтении текстов. Предлагается обучения грамматическим явлениям на основе вербальной правил-инструкции в сочетании со схематическими правилами. Теоретически обосновывается использования схематический правил в обучении рецептивным грамматическим явлениям английского языка, определены такие принципы как обобщенность, наглядность, конкретизированность, динамичность, репрезентативность, простота.

Ключевые слова: презентации, пассивная конструкция, правила-инструкций, схема, сочетании правил-инструкции со схемой, вербальная, обобщенность, наглядность, конкретизированность, динамичность, репрезентативность, простота, сознательность, гибкость, символ, схематизация, компонент, вспомогательный глагол, квантование.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of teaching English in non-linguistic faculties of higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan is to read texts on the specialty in English and extract the necessary information, as well as conduct an oral conversation on one's future specialty. Psychological

data show that students master a pattern of action through their own active actions with the subject being studied [Galperin 1966, p. 25]. At the same time, the decisive link that determines the course and quality of assimilation is the indicative part of the students' cognitive activity - the totality of those objective conditions that the student is guided by when performing actions.

This paper examines teaching Uzbek students of mathematics faculties passive constructions (hereinafter referred to as PCs) of the English language when reading texts. It is proposed to teach grammatical phenomena on the basis of verbal rules-instructions in combination with schematic rules. The use of schematic rules in teaching receptive grammatical phenomena of the English language is theoretically substantiated; principles such as generalization, clarity, specificity, dynamism, representativeness, and simplicity are defined.

LITERATURE REVIEW: In the theory of skills and abilities in a foreign language, it is possible to distinguish four main stages of work on grammatical material.

1. Stage of presentation of grammatical phenomena and creation of an indicative basis for the subsequent formation of skills.
2. Formation of speech grammatical skills by automating them in oral speech.
3. Inclusion of speech skills in different types of speech.
4. Development of speech skills.

Since this work addresses the issue of presentation of grammatical material, we will dwell on the first stage in more detail.

The purpose of the first stage is to create an indicative basis for the subsequent formation of grammatical skills. It is formed in the process of: 1) presenting it in oral and written speech (speech sample, speech microtext) in order to demonstrate its communicative function; 2) familiarization with methods of education, the meaning and scope of its use; 3) primary execution of actions involving a given phenomenon, according to a pattern without a rule, or according to a pattern and a rule.

The form of presentation (can be oral or written) is selected taking into account the following factors: firstly, the stage of learning (initial, intermediate, final) and secondly, the difficulty (complexity) of the grammatical material. Thirdly, depending on the purpose of learning: active mastery of the material or passive knowledge of it.

As is known, the indicative basis for teaching grammatical phenomena in reading is external formal signs. They are explained in the training rule, and the training rules may be:

- 1) verbal and schematic [Malishevskaya, 1973, pp. 34-43];
- 2) algorithmic and heuristic [Pepelyaev, 1980, p. 95];
- 3) descriptive and rules-instructions [Theoretical foundations..., 1981, p. 395].

Let's consider each opposition separately. In the first opposition, based on the attribute "words or diagram," verbal and schematic rules are distinguished. In our opinion, in teaching they should not be mutually exclusive. When demonstrating new grammatical material, the teacher briefly formulates a verbal rule, supporting it schematically. The latter, in our opinion, should remain in the student's field of vision throughout the first and part of the second stage of the formation of grammatical skills.

Analyzing the second opposition - algorithmic and heuristic rules, for our purposes we should unconditionally accept algorithmic rules that give clear instructions about the sequence and methods of performing grammatical actions.

In the third opposition, we must choose the instruction rule, since descriptive rules are heuristic in nature, and instruction rules are algorithmic.

Taking into account the tasks of teaching receptive grammar to Uzbek students in a non-linguistic university, as well as the existing experience in applying the types of rules mentioned above, we can conclude that for the presentation of receptive grammatical material it is necessary to use verbal rules-instructions that are algorithmic in nature and schematic rules.

Under the conditions of the described methodology for the presentation of passive constructions (hereinafter referred to as PCs) of the English language for reading literature, students in the specialty master actions with new PCs based on verbal rules-instructions formulated on the basis of modern requirements and principles, and graphically highlighted formal features of the construction, which aggregate and constitutes an indicative basis for the acquisition of grammatical actions.

In the scientific methodological literature there are a number of works that substantiate the use of these types of rules [Tsetlin 1961, Berman 1966, Gohlerner, Zhdan 1972, Ilyin 1975, Pepelyaev 1980, etc.]. Our goal was to consider presentations of grammatical phenomena in the English language for receptive acquisition based only on verbal rules-instructions and in combination of verbal rules-instructions with schematic rules. As noted in the scientific and methodological literature, the most rapid assimilation of a grammatical rule is achieved by its initial verbal formulation, which is consistent with the theory of the formation of mental actions [Berman, p. 395].

Having considered one of the options for presenting new grammatical material using rules and instructions [see. Begaliev 2022, pp. 288-290, 2022 pp. 134-137], let's focus on another version of the presentation, that is, rules-instructions in combination with schematic rules.

The scheme when teaching foreign languages greatly facilitates the process of generalizing grammatical relations and can act as an economical substitute for verbal structures [Sukhobskaya, 1988, pp. 273-274]. Schematization as a process is one of the main methods of grammatical abstraction, and therefore the scheme should become for students an instrument of action, a materialized form of grammatical abstraction. With the help of a diagram, a student can not only simultaneously capture the image of a phenomenon, but also build it according to the scheme, extract a scheme from a specific grammatical phenomenon. Schematization should become one of the ways students act with verbal material.

All of the above prompted us to develop a methodology for presenting passive constructions in the English language, which involves a combination of rules-instructions with a diagram.

Despite the fact that the effectiveness of using schemes in the formation of skills and the development of abilities has been repeatedly pointed out by psychologists [Sukhobskaya 1988, pp. 273-274, Tikhonov 1979, pp. 75-80, etc.], nevertheless, theoretical and practical issues of application schemes in the methodology of teaching foreign languages have been little studied. The existing work is scattered. The most complete requirements for schemes as a type of educational rule are formulated in the work of L.N. Malishevskaya [1973, pp. 34-43]. She systematized the following requirements for a schematized educational rule: 1) generality, 2) clarity, 3) specificity, 4) dynamism, 5) representativeness. As an additional requirement, the author puts forward the functional orientation of the scheme. However, this requirement is relevant for teaching reproductive grammatical material. When developing

receptive skills, in particular, grammatical reading skills, the student starts from the form that is already used in written speech in its corresponding function.

In our opinion, another most important requirement for the scheme should be its simplicity. If the schemes are complex, they will not speed up, but rather slow down the formation of grammatical skills, since students may get confused in complex and varied symbols.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS:

Let us consider separately each requirement and its implementation in our proposed educational schemes for mastering PC.

The generality of a scheme is understood as its ability to represent the essential and most characteristic features of a certain grammatical phenomenon by means of a sign system.

Visibility is the ability of a diagram to act as a visual support for abstraction, which provides a visual sensory basis for thinking, and also gives students the opportunity to more firmly assimilate a new structure.

To teach Uzbek students to understand English sentences from a PC, the first and second obligatory components (subject and predicate), as well as the third, optional component (indirect object) with a preceding preposition, should be designated with certain symbols. The remaining minor members of the sentence (if any), not included in the PC, can be designated by ellipses during schematization. This method of schematization clearly represents the essential and most characteristic features of a grammatical phenomenon.

Concretization follows from the generality and clarity of the diagram, since generality is achieved by abstracting from specific objects, from their non-essential features. In order to facilitate the process of forming an abstract generalization, the diagram should be specified with specific examples.

The dynamism of a schema refers to its ability to display a given grammatical phenomenon in interaction with others.

The qualities of concretization and dynamism in our case are embodied in the fact that each symbol specifically reflects a specific component of the PC. The use of ellipses to indicate minor members of sentences that are not included in the PC shows the interaction of PC with other grammatical phenomena.

Representativeness of the scheme is a certain external organization of the scheme in accordance with the psychophysiological characteristics of visual perception, that is, the use of color signals and symbolic indications: letters, numbers, arrows, stroke thickness, etc. In relation to PC training, this requirement is expressed in the designation of PC components with mathematical figures: rectangles, trapezoids, various triangles. This form of representation was chosen in accordance with the main specialty of mathematics students.

Given the requirement for simplicity, care should be taken when using color and symbolic indication. It is known from psychology that the use of too many colors and symbolic indications distracts attention. Therefore, we used a limited number of strict mathematical symbols, and the significant features of the PC were highlighted in color (red) when they were first presented in the microtext.

RESULTS: Taking into account the analyzed requirements, we have compiled educational schemes for teaching Uzbek students PC English for the purpose of reading literature in the specialty. When drawing up training schemes for recognizing PC English, its components and methods of transmission into the Uzbek language, the following minimum set of symbols was used:

The symbol denotes the first component of PC English.

The symbol , where the brackets indicate an affix that forms the passive voice.

The symbol denotes the third component, where a small equilateral triangle indicates the preposition by in English or the postpositions “bilan”, “tamonidan”, “tarafidan” - in Uzbek, and a large triangle - the agent.

The symbol indicates the auxiliary verb will.

The symbol indicates the auxiliary verb have\has.

The symbol указывает на модальный глагол can, may, must, have to, should.

The Roman numeral III indicates the third form of the semantic verb.

The ellipsis indicates minor members of the sentence that are not part of the PC.

In addition to the listed symbols, symbolic indications are also used - an equal sign, a plus, a question mark and an arrow indicating the direction of action. We believe that their meanings do not need clarification.

Familiarization with schemes begins when a new grammatical phenomenon is presented in a microtext. Reporting the first training instruction of rule-instruction No. 1, the teacher writes out sentences from the PC from the microtext, emphasizing its second component - the verb in the passive voice: The value of a fraction is not changed ...

... the numerator and denominator are multiplied ...

This is shown ...

It is called ...

Based on these examples, the teacher, together with the students, derives the “formula” of the second component of the PC:

is \ are + III = Present Indefinite Passive

The teacher then provides subsequent teaching instructions while introducing symbols representing the first, second, and third components of the PC.

When formulating training instructions “d”, “e” - about the negative and interrogative form of sentences with PC - the following schemes are also used: The value of a fraction is not changed

Are the numerator and denominator multiplied by the same number ?

It should be emphasized that the use of the diagram is especially important for explaining the order of translation of PC components from English into Uzbek languages, since the order of PC components in English and Uzbek languages is not the same. The use of a teaching scheme helps in overcoming this specific difficulty in teaching PC English to Uzbek students.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, having considered two options for presenting PC English: – based only on verbal rules-instructions [Begaliev 2022, pp. 288-290; Begaliev 2022 p.134-137] students master actions with new PCs of the English language based on verbal rules-instructions formulated on the basis of modern requirements and principles, and graphically highlighted formal features of the construction, which together constitute an indicative basis for the mastery of grammatical actions .

- based on the combination of verbal rules-instructions with educational diagrams, we can make an assumption about the advantages of the second option for teaching understanding of PC English to mathematics students, for whom reading diagrams is a habitual mental action and facilitates the process of learning the material. However, of course, this assumption should be tested experimentally.

In the process of PC presentation, the formation of the first stage of receptive grammatical skill occurs, the qualities of the skill such as “consciousness” and “flexibility” begin to form.

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